

Studies in Furan Derivatives: Part II*. Synthesis of some Bromobenzofuran Derivatives

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Bromination of methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methyl coumarilate (I) and its methyl ether and of methyl 6,7-dimethoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (II) has been studied. Bromination of the methyl ether of (I), and of (II) has also been studied with *N*-bromosuccinimide. The structures of the bromo derivatives have been proved by either degrading them to compounds of known structures or in the case of 3-bromomethyl derivatives by reaction with alkali, morpholine or acetic anhydride and sodium acetate.

The present work has been undertaken with a view to a systematic study of the pattern of substitution in benzofuran derivatives. Bromination of benzofuran and its derivatives has been investigated previously. For example, benzofuran was reported to give the unstable 2,3-dibromocoumaran¹⁻² on bromination while its 2-methyl and 3-phenyl derivatives gave 3-bromo³ and 2-bromo⁴ derivatives respectively. Potassium coumarilate on bromination gave the 2-bromo-derivative with the elimination of the carboxyl group⁵. Smith⁶ however found that coumarilic acid did not undergo bromination but its ethyl ester gave the 5-bromo derivative. Fries and Nohren⁷ brominated 6-hydroxy-3-methylbenzofuran and obtained a blue coloured compound to which no definite structure was assigned. On repetition of this work we also obtained similar results. Assuming that this is due to the high reactivity of the 2-position, it was thought of interest to study the substitution reactions using a compound in which the 2-position is blocked by a group which can be easily removed. 6-Hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid was therefore tried, but on bromination it also gave highly coloured and unworkable product. However, its methyl ester could be brominated smoothly and definite products were obtained.

Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (I), prepared by demethylation of methyl 6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate⁸ with anhydrous aluminium chloride, on bromination with one mole of bromine in acetic acid, gave the 7-bromo-derivative, which on methylation and hydrolysis yielded the known 7-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid⁹ as proved by direct comparison with an authentic specimen. On decarboxylation by heating with copper and quinoline or by heating above its melting point, it gave 7-bromo-6-methoxy-3-

*Part I, this *Journal*, 1966, 43, 437.

1. Stoermer and Kahlert., *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1633.

2. Fittig and Ebert., *Ann.*, 1882, 216, 162.

3. Claisen., *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 322.

4. Stoermer., *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1853.

5. Stoermer and Calov., *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 770..

6. Smith. *Iowa State Coll. J. Sc.*, 1937, 12, 155. *Chem. Abst.*, 1938, 32, 2938-

7. Fries and Nohren., *Ber.*, 1925, 58B, 1027.

8. Kostanecki and Lampe., *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1930.

9. Dalvi and Sethna., this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 359.

methyl benzofuran. The ester (I) on bromination with two moles of bromine in acetic acid gave the 5,7-dibromo derivative which on methylation and hydrolysis gave the known 5,7-dibromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid⁹ as proved by direct comparison with an authentic specimen. The decarboxylation of this acid with copper and quinoline or by heating above the melting point gave an untractable product. The methyl ether of (I) with one mole of bromine in acetic acid gave the 5-bromo-derivative. Attempt to demethylate it with aluminium chloride resulted in the formation of methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate. The 5-bromo-derivative on hydrolysis gave the known 5-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid⁹ as proved by direct comparison with an authentic sample. On decarboxylation by heating above the melting point it gave the known 5-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran, prepared previously by Limayo and Bhide¹⁰ by distilling the acid with calcium oxide. The same product was also obtained by the successive condensation of 2-acetyl-4-bromo-6-methoxyphenol¹¹ with ethyl bromoacetate to form ethyl 2-acetyl-4-bromo-6-methoxy-hydroxyacetate, hydrolysis of the ester and then simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation. The methyl ether of (I) on reaction with four moles of bromine in acetic acid gave methyl 3-bromomethyl-5-bromo-6-methoxycoumarilate. This was also obtained by the bromination of methyl 5-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate with *N*-bromosuccinimide. On action with alkali it gave 5-bromo-3-hydroxymethyl-6-methoxycoumarilic acid. The methyl ether of (I) with liquid bromine gave methyl 3-bromomethyl-5,7-dibromo-6-methoxycoumarilate, which with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave an acetoxy derivative with the loss of one bromine atom indicating that one bromine atom entered the side chain. The same tribromo derivative was obtained when methyl 5,7-dibromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate was brominated with *N*-bromosuccinimide.

Methyl 6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (II), prepared by esterification of the known 6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid¹², on bromination with one mole of bromine or with *N*-bromosuccinimide gave a monobromo derivative which on hydrolysis gave a monobromo acid different from the known 5-bromo-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid¹³. As the bromine was retained on heating with alkali and as the bromo-derivative remained unchanged when treated with morpholine or acetic anhydride and sodium acetate the bromine could not be in the side chain. The 4-bromo structure has therefore been assigned to this product. The 4-bromocoumarilic acid derivative on decarboxylation by heating above the melting point gave 4-bromo-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylbenzofuran. On bromination with four moles of bromine the ester (II) gave a dibromo derivative which has been assigned the 3-bromomethyl-4-bromo structure as it reacted with morpholine with the loss of one bromine atom. The same dibromo derivative was obtained when methyl 4-bromo-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilate was brominated with *N*-bromosuccinimide.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl 6-Hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate.—Methyl 6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1.0 g.) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.0 g.) and refluxed in dry benzene for 4 hr. It was cooled and dil. HCl was added to it. The product which separated was

10. Limayo and Bhide, *Rangamam*, 1938, 1, 136; *Chem. Abst.*, 1939, 33, 1699.

11. Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 261.

12. Sakai and Kato, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan.*, 1935, 55, 691; *Chem. Abst.*, 1935, 29, 7911.

13. Lele and Sethna, *J. Sc. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 101.

*All the m.p.s. are uncorrected.

crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 194°. (Found: C, 63.68; H, 4.78, $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.85%.)

Methyl 7-Bromo-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate.—Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (2.0 g.) in acetic acid (20.0 ml.) was treated with bromine (1.6 g.) in acetic acid (10.1 ml.) and kept for 5 hr. The reaction mixture on dilution with water gave a product which crystallised from dilute acetic acid, and had m.p. 189° (2.0 g.). (Found: Br, 28.42. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 28.07%.)

The methyl ether, prepared by refluxing with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone solution for 4 hr., was crystallised from acetic acid, and had m.p. 195°. (Found: C, 47.93; H, 3.44; Br, 20.99. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4Br$ requires C, 48.16; H, 3.68; Br, 26.75%.)

Methyl 7-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1.0 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20.0 ml.; 10%) on a steam bath for 1 hr. The product which separated on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 252°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid was not depressed.

7-Bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran.—7-Bromo-6-methoxy-3-methyl coumarilic acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (6.0 ml.) for 1 hr. on a sand bath. The product which separated on pouring the mixture in dil. HCl was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 81°. (Found: C, 49.73; H, 3.62; Br, 33.20. $C_{10}H_8O_4Br$ requires C, 49.79; H, 3.74; Br, 33.26%.)

Methyl 5,7-Dibromo-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate.—Methyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (15.0 ml.) was treated with bromine (1.60 g.) in acetic acid (16.0 ml.). The reaction mixture was left overnight. The product separating was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, (1.0 g.), m.p. 231°. (Found: Br, 44.24. $C_{11}H_8O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 43.95%.)

The methyl ether, prepared by methylation with dimethyl sulphate, was crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 142-43°. (Found: C, 37.90; H, 2.55; Br, 41.89. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4Br_2$ requires C, 38.10; H, 2.65; Br, 42.33%.)

The above ether (1.0 g.) on heating with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20.0 ml.; 10%) on a steam bath for 1 hr. gave the 5,7-dibromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid, m.p. 268°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen was not depressed.

Methyl 5-Bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate.—Methyl-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1.1 g.) in acetic acid (10.0 ml.) was treated with bromine (0.8 g.) in acetic acid (8.0 ml.). The product separated within 1/2 hr. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles (1.0 g.), m.p. 158°. (Found: Br, 27.15. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires Br, 26.75%.)

Methyl 5-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (0.5 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20.0 ml.; 10%) for 1/2 hr. on a steam bath. The product which separated on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid, and had m.p. 256°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 5-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methyl coumarilic acid was not depressed.

5-Bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran.—5-Bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid (1.0 g.) was heated in an oil bath above its melting point till the effervescence ceased

(5 min.). The product crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 74°. Limaye and Bhilde² reported m.p. 70°. (Found: C, 49.33; H, 3.62; Br, 33.02. $C_{10}H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 49.79; H, 3.74; Br, 33.26%.)

Ethyl 2-Acetyl-4-bromo-5-methoxyphenoxyacetate. — 2-Acetyl-4-bromo-5-methoxyphenol (2.45 g.) was dissolved in acetone (50.0 ml.) and refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (1.67 g.) for 6 hr. On evaporation of acetone, the reaction mixture was added to water and the product which separated was washed with dilute alkali and crystallised from alcohol. It had m.p. 140-41°. (Found: C, 47.17; H, 4.55; Br, 24.17. $C_{13}H_{13}O_5Br$ requires C, 47.13; H, 4.53; Br, 24.17%.)

2-Acetyl-4-bromo-5-methoxyphenoxyacetic Acid. — Ethyl-2-acetyl-4-bromo-5-methoxyphenoxyacetate (0.5 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20.0 ml.; 10%) for 2 hr. on a steam bath. The resulting solution was cooled and acidified. The product which separated was crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 226-27°. (Found: C, 43.54; H, 3.65; Br, 26.16. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires C, 43.57; H, 3.63; Br, 26.46%.)

The above acid (1.0 g.) when heated with acetic anhydride (7.0 ml.) and sodium acetate (1.5 g.) for 1½ hr. on a sand bath gave 5-bromo-6-methoxy-2-methylbenzofuran described before.

Methyl 3-Bromomethyl 5-bromo-6-methoxycoumarilate. — Methyl-6-methoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (1.1 g.) in acetic acid (10.0 ml.) was treated with bromine (3.2 g.) in acetic acid (16.0 ml.) and heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product which separated crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 210°. (Found: Br, 41.96. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 42.33%.)

The same product was obtained when methyl 5-bromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.5 g.) in chloroform was treated with N-bromosuccinimide (0.5 g.) and the reaction mixture refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hr.

5-Bromo-3-hydroxymethyl-6-methoxycoumarilic Acid. — Methyl 3-bromomethyl-5-bromo-6-methoxycoumarilate (1.0 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide solution (20.0 ml.; 10%) on a steam bath for 8 hr. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from acetic acid and, had m.p. 226°. (Found: C, 43.66; H, 3.22; Br, 26.81. $C_{11}H_9O_5Br$ requires C, 43.85; H, 2.99; Br, 26.58%.)

Methyl 3-Bromomethyl-5, 7-dibromo-6-methoxycoumarilate. — Methyl 6-methoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (2.0 g.) was treated gradually with liquid bromine (3.0 ml.) and kept overnight. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and treated with sodium bisulphite to remove excess of bromine, and then treated with sodium hydroxide solution to remove demethylated product, if any. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 168°. (Found: Br, 52.99. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br_3$ requires Br, 52.52%.)

The same tribromo derivative was also obtained when methyl-5, 7-dibromo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.5 g.) was refluxed with N-bromosuccinimide (0.5 g.) in chloroform solution for 6 hr.

Methyl 3-Acetoxyethyl-5, 7-dibromo-6-methoxycoumarilate. — Methyl-3-bromo methyl 5, 7-dibromo-6-methoxy coumarilate (1.0 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (4.0 ml.) and sodium acetate (2.0 g.) for 1 hr. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was added to

water and the product crystallised from dilute acetic acid and had m.p. 154°. (Found: C, 38.44; H, 2.55; Br, 36.44. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6Br_2$ requires C, 38.53; H, 2.75; Br, 36.69%).

Methyl 6, 7-Dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilate. — 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-methyl coumarilic acid (2.30 g.) was dissolved in acetone (50.0 ml.) and refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (1.26 g.) for 3 hr. On evaporation of acetone, the reaction mixture was added to water and the product which separated crystallised from dilute acetic acid and had m.p. 96°. (Found: C, 62.07; H, 5.57; $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.40; H, 5.66%).

Methyl 4-Bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilate. — Methyl-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (2.5 g.) in acetic acid (25.0 ml.) was treated with bromine (1.6 g.) in acetic acid (10.0 ml.). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 hr. The product which separated was crystallised from acetic acid in needles (2.4 g.), m.p. 129-30°. (Found: Br, 24.05. $C_{15}H_{13}O_5Br$ requires Br, 24.32%).

The same bromo derivative was obtained when methyl 6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl-coumarilate (0.5 g.) was treated with N-bromosuccinimide (0.5 g.) and the mixture refluxed in chloroform solution for 6 hr.

4-Bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilic Acid. — The above ester (1.0 g.) on heating with sodium hydroxide solution (20.0 ml., 10%) on a steam bath for 1 hr. gave 4-bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid which crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 239-40°. (Found: C, 45.33; H, 3.28; Br, 25.67. $C_{14}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires C, 45.72; H, 3.49; Br, 25.40%).

4-Bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methylbenzofuran. — 4-Bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl-coumarilic acid (1.0 g.) was heated in an oil bath above its melting point till the effervescence ceased (5 min.). The product crystallised from dilute alcohol and had m.p. 59°. (Found: C, 49.01; H, 3.72; Br, 29.54. $C_{17}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires C, 48.71; H, 4.06; Br, 29.55%).

Methyl 3-Bromo-methyl-4-bromo-6, 7-dimethoxycoumarilate. — Methyl-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (2.5 g.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid (25.0 ml.) and the solution was treated with bromine (6.4 g.) in acetic acid (32.0 ml.). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 1 hr. and then heated for 1 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on dilution with water crystallised from acetic acid in needles (1.2 g.) m.p. 138°. (Found: Br, 39.20. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5Br_2$ requires Br, 39.21%).

The same dibromo derivative was obtained when methyl 4-bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl coumarilate (0.5 g.) was treated with N-bromosuccinimide (0.5 g.) and the mixture refluxed in chloroform solution for 6 hr.

Methyl 4-Bromo-3-morpholinomethyl-6, 7-dimethoxycoumarilate. — Methyl 3-bromo-methyl 4-bromo-6, 7-dimethoxy coumarilate (0.5 g.) was treated with morpholine (0.5 g.) and the mixture refluxed in alcohol solution for 1 hr. The product which separated crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 128°. (Found: Br, 19.31; N, 3.25. $C_{17}H_{20}O_6BrN$ requires Br, 19.32; N, 3.38%).

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